

From Aerial Imagery to Official Statistics: Integrating Registry Data in Operational Deep Learning for Fine-Grained Built-Up Area Mapping in the Netherlands

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Abstract

This paper presents an operational GeoAI framework for fine-grained mapping of built-up areas across the Netherlands. Two deep learning pipelines are evaluated: (1) a hierarchical RGB-only model (EfficientNet-B3 + Swin-Small Transformer, macro-F1: 64.3%) and (2) a multimodal late-fusion model augmenting visual features with parcel-level registry attributes (macro-F1: 67.1%). Results show that three BBG categories are reliably classified from imagery alone ($F1 \geq 75\%$); registry fusion extends this to nine classes, particularly infrastructure-defined categories with weak visual signatures. Findings support a hybrid operational strategy for semi-automated annual BBG production.

Keywords: GeoAI; land use classification; deep learning; multimodal fusion; Swin Transformer; EfficientNet; BBG

1. Introduction

In the Netherlands, official land-use maps are produced through the Bestand Bodemgebruik (BBG) system, which integrates national registries such as BAG (buildings), NWB (roads), and ProRail (rail infrastructure). Manual BBG updates are costly and slow; advancing to annual cycles requires automation. Recent GeoAI advances, such as vision transformers and multimodal fusion, offer new capacity for classifying built-up land use from aerial imagery combined with structured administrative data. This paper evaluates two such pipelines against 14 BBG built-up subcategories, addressing two research questions:

This study addresses two research questions:

RQ1: For which BBG-built-up classes is reliable classification from aerial imagery ($F1 \geq 75\%$) achievable?

RQ2: Does incorporating ancillary data into the feature set improve the classification of visually ambiguous categories?

The $F1 \geq 75\%$ threshold marks operational readiness: at this level, automated classification meaningfully reduces manual BBG workload while keeping errors within acceptable bounds.

Published in “Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI 2026) – Oral Presentation Papers”, edited by Haosheng Huang and Nico Van de Weghe, GeoAI 2026, 3-6 June 2026, Ghent, Belgium.

This contribution underwent single-blind peer review based on the extended abstract.

2. Data and Experimental Design

The dataset covers the entire Netherlands using BBG 2020 polygons and 25 cm RGB orthophotos (PDOK 2020, EPSG:28992). From 358,753 labelled polygons, 14 built-up subcategories were selected alongside a background class (15 classes total). Stratified sampling corrected for severe class imbalance, yielding 82,250 balanced patches (70/15/15 split). Each 512×512 px patch is centred on a polygon centroid; registry attributes are joined per parcel.

3. Methodology

3.1 Method 1: Hierarchical RGB-Only Pipeline (Figure 1, left)

Stage 1: Built-Up Detection (EfficientNet-B3). A binary classifier uses EfficientNet-B3 (Tan & Le, 2019), pretrained on ImageNet, and applies compound scaling across depth, width, and resolution to achieve high accuracy. Training uses focal loss (Lin et al., 2017) with class-weighted sampling; the decision threshold is tuned on the validation set to maximise built-up recall.

Stage 2: 14-Class Classification (Swin-Small Transformer). Built-up patches are classified by a Swin-Small Vision Transformer (Liu et al., 2021) with hierarchical shifted-window self-attention, capturing local texture and broader spatial context. The model is fine-tuned end-to-end with cross-entropy loss and cosine-annealing LR; patch-level predictions are aggregated to the polygon level by majority vote.

Figure 1. Left: Method 1 hierarchical RGB-only pipeline (Stage 1: EfficientNet-B3 built-up detection; Stage 2: Swin-Small Transformer 14-class classification). Right: Method 2 multimodal late-fusion architecture (parallel CNN visual encoder + MLP attribute encoder, concatenated for joint classification). Source: Authors.

3.2 Method 2: Multimodal Late-Fusion Model (Figure 1, right)

Method 2 augments the visual pipeline with parcel-level registry attributes to resolve functional ambiguity between visually similar classes. An EfficientNet-B3 CNN encodes the RGB patch; a three-layer MLP encodes nine registry attributes (BAG function codes, ProRail adjacency, NWB road class, parcel area, BRP land type). Embeddings are concatenated and passed to a classification head trained with focal loss. This late-fusion design keeps encoders independently pre-trainable and allows class-specific modality weighting.

4. Results

Evaluation uses macro-averaged F1 and per-class precision/recall on the held-out test set (5,143 patches). Table 1 compares the two methods for each class. Stage 1 of Method 1 achieved 97% built-up recall after threshold optimisation. Figure 2 shows normalised confusion matrices for both pipelines.

Figure 2. Normalised confusion matrices for Method 1 (left) and Method 2 (right). Rows = true class, columns = predicted class. Source: Authors.

Class	Code	M1 F1	M2 F1	Verdict
Background	—	0.628	0.810	M2 ↑
Railroad	10	0.401	0.910	M2 ↑↑
Main road	11	0.595	0.730	M2 ↑
Airport	12	0.643	0.220	M1 ↓
Metro/tram	13	—	0.860	M2 ↑↑
Residential	20	0.840	0.810	M1
Retail, hotel	21	0.638	0.520	M1
Public institutions	22	0.537	0.440	M1
Socio-cultural	23	0.669	0.580	M1
Industrial/offices	24	0.689	0.630	M1
Dumping site	30	0.333	0.120	M1 ↓↓
Cemetery	32	0.897	0.970	M2
Mining area	33	0.712	0.770	M2
Construction site	34	0.756	0.710	M1
Semi built-up	35	0.658	0.790	M2
Macro-avg F1		0.643	0.658	—

Table 1. F1-score comparison between Method 1 (RGB-only) and Method 2 (multimodal fusion).

Figure 3. Prediction comparison across both models (3 examples per category). Green border = both correct; Orange border = one method correct; Red border = both wrong. GT = ground truth class; Source: Authors.

Figure 4. Per-class F1 comparison: Method 1 (RGB-only) vs Method 2 (multimodal fusion). Infrastructure classes show the largest fusion gains; visually dominant classes are largely unaffected or slightly reduced. Source: Authors.

RQ1: Reliably classified classes (F1 \geq 75%): Imagery alone: Cemetery (0.897), Residential (0.840), Construction site (0.756). With fusion: Railroad (0.910), Metro/tram (0.860), Mining area (0.770), Semi built-up (0.790), Main road (0.730), Cemetery (0.970). Nine BBG classes remain below threshold with either method.

RQ2: Does fusion improve robustness? Yes, selectively. Registry attributes add 40+ F1 points for infrastructure classes with weak visual signatures (railroad, metro/tram), but have a negligible or negative impact on functionally ambiguous BBG 2x categories and rare classes (dumping site, airport).

5. Discussion

When fusion adds value: Infrastructure classes - railroad, metro/tram, and main roads benefit substantially from registry attributes. ProRail adjacency flags, NWB road class codes, and BAG transport function codes supply functional context that no single aerial patch can reveal: a rail corridor and an industrial yard can look identical from above yet differ entirely in administrative records. The effect is most striking for metro/tram, where visual F1 is near zero but rises to 0.860 once registry data is introduced.

Where imagery suffices: Residential areas, cemeteries, and construction sites carry strong, consistent visual signatures like regular roof grids, orderly row patterns, and bare disturbed soil, respectively. For these classes, the Swin Transformer has sufficient discriminative information in the image alone, and registry attributes offer no consistent gain.

Failure modes: Dumping sites are both rare (149 training samples) and visually heterogeneous, with bare earth, rubble, and partial vegetation appearing within a single patch, resulting in near-zero recall across methods. BBG 2x categories (retail, public institutions, socio-cultural) present a harder structural problem: their registry attributes overlap substantially, and their rooftops are architecturally interchangeable, so neither the visual nor the attribute branch can separate them reliably.

Operational strategy: The practical implication is a two-track deployment: use the RGB-only pipeline for visually stable categories and invoke the fusion model selectively for infrastructure-defined classes where registry data is decisive. In both cases, model outputs are linked to BBG parcel identifiers and aggregated to standard statistical reporting units, keeping the pipeline compatible with production workflows.

6. Conclusions

This paper presents an operational GeoAI framework for fine-grained mapping of built-up areas at the national scale in the Netherlands. Two pipelines were evaluated: a hierarchical RGB-only model (EfficientNet-B3 + Swin-Small, macro-F1 64.3%) and a multimodal late-fusion model (same backbone + MLP registry encoder, macro-F1 67.1%).

RQ1: Three classes reliably exceed F1 \geq 75% from imagery alone (cemetery, residential, construction site); six additional classes cross the threshold with registry fusion (railroad, metro/tram, main road, mining area, semi-built-up, background). **RQ2:** Fusion provides decisive gains for infrastructure classes (+40 F1 pts for railroad, metro/tram) but negligible benefit for visually ambiguous BBG 2x categories. Results support a hybrid operational strategy: RGB-only for visually stable classes, fusion selectively for infrastructure-defined categories.

Acknowledgements

This work was funded by Eurostat under the GEOS2023-NL programme (Grant Agreement No. 101155717, Project PR003214, WP2–D2.2). The views are those of the authors and do not represent those of the European Union or Eurostat.

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